

**Effecting Change in Long-Standing Institutions:
Inuit Employment and Labour Relations at Voisey's Bay.**

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Acronyms

BCTU – Building and Construction Trades Unions

IBA – Impact Benefit Agreement

LIA – Labrador Inuit Association

LILCA – Labrador Inuit Land Claim Agreement

NG – Nunatsiavut Government

RDC – Resource Development Council

SPA – Special Project Agreement

USW – United Steelworkers

VBNC – Voisey’s Bay Nickel Company

Executive Summary

The resolution of Comprehensive Land Claims and Impact Benefit Agreements has altered the industrial relations environment in Canada's north. This research project examines the changing institutional framework governing work in Labrador to identify challenges and successes in the provision of high quality employment for Inuit. More specifically, the report examines how unions interacted with provisions in the Impact Benefit Agreement and their enforcement by the Nunatsiavut Government.

Prior to the 1970s, three institutions governed resource employment in Canada: employers, the state, and unions. More recently, as Aboriginal governments and institutions had gained greater control over resource development in their territories, they have become important new players in employment governance. The success of Aboriginal governments in ensuring that their members obtain quality employment and training opportunities, however, remains contingent on their relationships with unions, employers, and the state. Since Aboriginal peoples have had varied experiences with unions it is important to ask how unions are interacting with Impact Benefit Agreements.

This report addresses these questions by presenting results of a case study of Inuit employment at Voisey's Bay. Over three summers (2009, 2010, and 2011) the research team interviewed 35 workers at Voisey's Bay and 40 key informants including representatives from unions, the Nunatsiavut Government, the provincial government, and Vale Inco. Interview materials were supplemented with news reports, collective agreements, and other written materials. These materials provided the context for an analysis of the institutional relationships that developed between labour unions and the Nunatsiavut Government during the construction and operations phases of the project. Moreover, worker interviews were used to gauge how worker perceived the roles of each institution in their employment.

Industrial relations at Voisey's Bay were influenced by the recent changes in the structure of the mining industry. In the early 21st century, the mining industry became more concentrated. Large firms such as BHP Billiton, Xstrata, and Rio Tinto have 'quickly swallowed up smaller rivals in the attempt to take more market share, boost capital assets, and diversify their operations' (Peters, 2011, p. 82). Consolidation allowed firms to strengthen their control over the supply and pricing of commodities and lower their dependence on any one operation. Other changes to industry structure include: the increased use of increasingly subcontractors to provide key mine services; the use of fly-in, fly-out models of labour supply; and more capital intensive mines requiring smaller and more highly skilled workforces. All of these changes have increased the negotiating power of corporations while reducing that of labour unions, and in some cases, governments.

With rising Nickel prices in the early 2000s, the Voisey's Bay Nickel Company had a strong incentive to complete the construction of the project quickly. To ensure a steady supply of skilled labour, the company signed a Special Project Agreement with the Resource Development Council representing the building and construction trades unions. This agreement required that contractors use only unionized labour on site. Inuit and Innu who

met the skill requirements were required to join the union prior to working on site. In the absence of a clearly defined process to follow the order of preference in hiring, employer practices were 'business as usual' at the outset of construction. Tensions developed as the Nunatsiavut Government and the employer struggled to implement the order of preference in hiring. Some trade unions wanted to ensure that their members who were predominantly from Newfoundland had opportunities to work in the province. Contractors and some members of the Resource Development Council were also concerned about maintaining the quality of their work and meeting construction schedules set out by the Voisey's Bay Nickel Company; objectives that they felt would be difficult when working with people who they did not train. Alternatively, the Nunatsiavut Government saw the employment benefits of development on their traditional territories going to outsiders. These tensions were intensified by the geographical separation of Labrador and Newfoundland and the organizational structure of the building and construction trade unions. These unions were almost all based in St. John's NL, and very few had undertaken any organizing work in Labrador prior to the project.

The organizational structure of the building and construction trades unions posed challenges to the inclusion of new Aboriginal workers. Trade unions mitigate the instability experienced by workers in construction, an industry that typically undergoes cyclical and seasonal fluctuations. They increase worker security and wellbeing by facilitating the movement between jobs, providing a pension and benefit plan independent of any individual employer, providing mechanisms for dispute resolution, and assisting workers financially through apprenticeship schooling. Trade unions gain union power by being able to provide employers with access to skilled workers. The latter is achieved using a hiring list. Because the ability to acquire work depends on the number of people on the hiring list, in the short-term, members' interests are served by restricting membership. The need to differentiate themselves from unskilled workers and control hiring along with the regional identification of Newfoundlanders created barriers to the acceptance of the order of preference provisions in the Impact Benefit Agreement.

In general, implementing the order of preference was more successful during the operations phase. Inuit were represented on the bargaining committee and the union executive and the order of preference was articulated in the collective agreements, albeit without reference to adjacency or gender (Appendix A). However, the Nunatsiavut Government and the United Steelworkers had conflicting understandings of their jurisdiction over employment. Differences arose from the objectives and roles of each organization. Since the Nunatsiavut Government was responsible to all Labrador Inuit, not only those working at Voisey's Bay, they were concerned with equality among Inuit and with ensuring that Impact Benefit Agreement provisions remained intact. In particular, the Nunatsiavut Government wanted to ensure that Impact Benefit Agreement provisions were not extended to non-Inuit workers through their inclusion in collective agreements. In general, the Nunatsiavut Government favoured a sharp distinction between their role and that of the union. Alternatively, the United Steelworkers saw the division of institutional roles in employment as more fluid, and wanted to strengthen Impact Benefit Agreement provisions by negotiating them into collective agreements. Moreover, during the strike, the United Steelworkers felt that the Nunatsiavut Government was neglecting the interests of

Inuit workers by not placing pressure on the Voisey' Bay Nickel Company to facilitate the resolution of industrial relations disputes.

The discrepancy in these perspectives was reflected in worker responses. Three themes emerged from worker interviews: access to employment, training, and lack of clarity in workplace governance. All Inuit and Innu workers and several non-Aboriginal workers believed in and respected the order of preference for hiring and promotion. Inuit workers often saw the relationship to territory as a more important criterion for employment than skills and qualifications. Alternatively, most non-Aboriginal workers and building and construction trades union representatives felt that qualifications should be considered in employment decisions, and some felt that it should be the only criterion for employment. These divergent perspectives suggested a difference in values. Some Inuit suggested that people who were very qualified should have less priority for employment since they would be able to get other work and therefore did not require assistance. This reflected a broad view of equality and sharing that was not present in the comments of non-Aboriginal workers who often drew on narrow understandings of equality that were reliant on meritocracy.

Inuit workers often felt that gaps in qualifications between Inuit and non-Aboriginal peoples needed to be addressed for Inuit to fully benefit from employment opportunities at the mine. In particular, they felt that Inuit and Innu on the coast continued to face barriers to accessing training and that the Voisey' Bay Nickel Company and its contractors should ensure for more on-the-job training. Lastly, Inuit workers had conflicting understandings of the roles that unions and the Nunatsiavut Government played in their employment. At first, some Inuit workers were unsure whether to approach the Inuit and Innu Employment Coordinators (company employees to address on-site IBA concerns) or the shop stewards with employment-related grievances. Moreover, several Inuit expressed that they wanted a greater amount of support from the Nunatsiavut Government during the strike. Others, however, felt that the strike was not the responsibility of the Nunatsiavut Government.

In conclusion, this report suggests that unions have an important role to play in Aboriginal employment but that this role is one of supporting – and not appropriating – the Aboriginal government's role in employment. In particular, the building and construction trades unions are in an ideal position to facilitate the training and employment of Aboriginal workers because of their role in training and facilitating movement between jobs.

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Introduction

How are labour unions interacting with new institutions to increase Aboriginal employment in Canada's north? This report examines employment relations between unions, the Nunatsiavut Government (NG) and the Voisey's Bay Nickel Company (VBNC),¹ during the construction and operations phases at the Voisey's Bay nickel mine in Labrador with the goal of increasing quality work opportunities for Labrador Inuit. Specifically, it focuses on how interactions between labour unions and employment provisions in the Impact Benefit Agreement² (IBA) between the NG and the VBNC affected Aboriginal employment and workers' experiences.

Aboriginal communities use IBAs to benefit from resource development. IBAs contain provisions for the transfer of royalties, business opportunities, and employment to Aboriginal communities in exchange for access to resources. Since they contain provisions for training, hiring, retention, and promotion of Aboriginal workers, IBAs overlap with collective agreements between employers and unions. For example, ensuring that local Aboriginal people have preferential access to hiring, promotion, and training may be incommensurate with union seniority clauses designed to safeguard workers against employer discrimination. Alternatively, union goals to create workplace democracy and improve the material conditions of work may also maintain the value and desirability of the employment benefits contained in IBAs.

Aboriginal governments and unions are important partners in resource-based economic development in Canada's north. Given the significance of IBAs and collective agreements to quality employment for Aboriginal workers, it is critical to understand how these institutions are experienced and perceived by Aboriginal workers. It is also important to understand where challenges to implementing an IBA exist, and what steps can be taken to overcome these challenges.

In this report we address the questions:

1. How well are unions and Aboriginal governments working together to promote Aboriginal employment?
2. How do workers perceive the roles and relationships of unions and the NG in employment at Voisey's Bay?

These questions are addressed through a case study of Inuit employment at Voisey's Bay. Although the details of this case are in many ways unique, the Voisey's Bay development

¹ The Voisey's Bay Nickel Company was originally a subsidiary of Inco. Vale acquired Inco and its affiliated subsidiaries in 2006.

² An IBA is a confidential and binding contractual agreement between Aboriginal governments and employers outlining compensation that the former will receive in exchange for permitting industrial development in their traditional territories (Sosa and Keenan, 2001).

also resembles other resource development projects in the north. Since the resource to be developed was located on unceded Aboriginal lands, resource development was interwoven with the negotiation and signing of modern treaties and required the signing of IBAs.

In 1993, massive nickel deposits were discovered at *Tasiujatsoak*, within the traditional territories of the Labrador Inuit and the Labrador Innu at Voisey's Bay. VBNC acquired the mineral rights to the area despite unresolved land claims that the Labrador Innu and the Labrador Inuit Association (LIA) filed with the Government of Newfoundland and Labrador and the Ministry of Indian Affairs and Northern Development in the 1970s. Throughout the 1990s, the LIA asserted their territorial rights using a court injunction and protest to ensure that an Environmental Assessment was completed, that progress was made with land claim negotiations, and that they had adequate leverage to negotiate their interest in an IBA. In 2002, the LIA signed the IBA, confident that their land claim was secure. Very shortly after, the VBNC began construction of the mine and mill. Ore from Voisey's Bay was first processed in August 2005. The Labrador Inuit Land Claim Agreement (LILCA) came into effect in December of 2005, creating the NG. Although the IBA and LILCA both contain employment provisions, the IBA is the principle instrument used by the NG to govern Aboriginal employment.

Two distinct phases of employment relations at Voisey's Bay are distinguishable: construction (2002-2005) and extraction and processing (2005-present). During the construction phase workers represented by different building and construction trades unions (BCTUs), who were together organized under the Resource Development Council (RDC) were employed by a network of construction and engineering contractors. During the second phase, ore was mined and processed by VBNC. Employees worked directly for VBNC or for contractors. Many of these employees were governed by collective agreements between VBNC or related contractors and the United Steelworkers (USW). A strike by several of the bargaining units covered by USW collective agreements is of great significance during this phase.

The report is organized as follows. Following the methodology, the first section briefly discusses the relationships between trade, industrial, and public sector unions and Aboriginal workers in Canada. This section concludes that more research is necessary to better understand how industrial relations processes are evolving in response to IBAs. The second section describes the evolution of the global mining industry as it relates to Voisey's Bay. The third section maps the industrial relations environment at VBNC focusing on relations between VBNC, the BCTUs and the USW. The fourth section adopts an institutional perspective to analyze the roles and relationships of unions and the NG in employment. The fifth section describes the perspectives of workers at Voisey's Bay. In the sixth and final section we conclude with an overview of our findings and considerations for NG's future relationships with unions.

Although the report focuses primarily on Inuit workers, we recognize that many of the issues of concern are also applicable to Innu, Métis, and other Aboriginal workers,

governments, and communities. However, the remainder of the report refers only to the IBA between the NG and VBNC.

Methodology

This report draws upon interviews with workers and a variety of key informants. Seventy-five interviews were conducted during the springs and summers of 2009, 2010, and 2011. Inuit advisors and an Inuit research assistant in Nain helped design the interview schedules and draft lists of potential interviewees. An Inuit research assistant coordinated and helped conduct interviews in Nain. Interview subjects in Goose Bay and St. John’s were recruited through a combination of word-of-mouth referrals from NG representatives, snowball sampling, and from picket lines during the 2009-2011 strike between the USW and Vale. Interviews with key informants were open-ended and designed to elicit conversation. Interviews with workers were semi-structured. In general, subjects discussed their perceptions regarding employment relations as they related the impacts of the IBA, Vale (and Inco), and unions.

Of these interviews, twenty subjects were bargaining unit members employed by VBNC, sixteen were bargaining unit members employed by affiliated contractors, twelve were business agents or paid full-time representatives of trade unions, seven were full-time representatives of the USW, six were current or former representatives of the NG, five were managers or owners of affiliated contractors, and four were managers at VBNC. Five subjects were classified as other. This group included representatives of quasi-governmental regulatory or development agencies and politicians. This sample is illustrated in Table 1. Seventy interviews were conducted in person and five were conducted by telephone.

Table 1 – Interview Subjects by Occupation

VBNC – Operations	Contractor	Trade Union	USW	NG	VBNC – Management	Contractor – Management	Other
20	16	12	7	6	4	5	5

Fifty-three interview subjects were male and twenty-two were female. The vast majority of subjects employed directly by the VBNC and those employed as full-time representatives of trade unions or the USW were male. Twelve female subjects identified as Inuit and three female subjects identified as Innu. Female subjects were most likely to be employed by contractors.

Thirty subjects identified as non-Aboriginal, thirty-nine identified as Inuit, and six identified as Innu. The majority of subjects that identified as Inuit were employed directly by VBNC or by affiliated contractors. Most of this group also worked at Voisey’s Bay during the construction phase. All of the subjects that identified as Innu were employed by an affiliated contractor, and all had experience working at Voisey’s Bay during both the construction and operations phases. All of the NG representatives identified as Inuit. Only

one trade union representative identified as Inuit. Three USW representatives identified as Inuit. Two contractors and two VBNC managers identified as Inuit. The gender and ethnicity of subjects are illustrated in Table 2.

Thirty-four interview subjects resided permanently in or near Happy Valley-Goose Bay (including Sheshatshiu). Sixteen resided permanently in Nain. Twenty resided permanently in Newfoundland. Four resided elsewhere in Canada and one resided in the US. All subjects from Nain identified as Inuit, as did twenty-three residents of Happy Valley-Goose Bay. The six Innu subjects resided in Sheshatshiu. None of the subjects from Newfoundland, the rest of Canada, or the US identified as Aboriginal. The residency of interview subjects is illustrated in Table 3.

Table 2 – Interview Subjects by Gender and Ethnicity

Inuit		Innu		Non-Aboriginal	
<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>
27	12	3	3	23	7

Table 3 – Interview Subjects by Residency

Happy Valley-Goose Bay/Sheshatshiu	Nain	Newfoundland	Other Canada	US
34	16	20	4	1

1. Unions and Aboriginal Workers

Prior to the 1970s, three institutions governed resource employment in Canada: employers, the state, and unions. Aboriginal peoples were often excluded from resource industries and received little benefit from the extraction of minerals and resource located on their traditional lands. However, recent legislative changes brought about by the efforts of Aboriginal communities have required that governments and employers recognize the legitimacy of territorial claims, particularly as they relate to natural resources. Consequently, many Aboriginal communities have gained greater control over resource extraction industries. The success of Aboriginal governments in ensuring that their members obtain quality employment and training opportunities, however, remains contingent on their relationships with unions, employers, and the state.

Aboriginal peoples' experiences with unions have varied. Throughout most of the 20th century, private sector unions catered primarily to white males of European descent. The practices of these unions displayed both structural and overt racism towards Aboriginal peoples. Some research describes union members' racist depictions of Aboriginal peoples as non-workers or as being outside of the working-class (Guard, 2004; Dunk, 1994). There are select instances, however, where private sector unions included Aboriginal peoples. For instance, many Iroquois ironworkers belonged to the International Association of Bridge, Structural, and Ornamental Iron Workers in the first half of the 20th century (Mitchell, 1960), and many Aboriginal loggers and sawmill workers in British Columbia belonged to

the International Association of Woodworkers (Neufeld and Parnaby, 2000). More recently, some private sector unions – particularly the USW – have included terms and conditions specific to Aboriginal culture in collective agreements with employers in northern regions.

Public sector unions have generally been more proactive in engaging Aboriginal peoples. This is consistent with the broader agendas of equity and social justice common to such unions. Teachers' unions in Ontario and Quebec made demands related to the linguistic rights of Aboriginal students and for increases in the number of Aboriginal teachers in public schools in the north (Corporation des Enseignants du Québec, 1973; McCue, 1992). Other public sector unions, such as the Public Service Alliance of Canada and the Canadian Union of Public Employees have Aboriginal committees and seats at various levels within their organizational structures. This has resulted in demonstrations of solidarity with Aboriginal struggles as well as in the development of Aboriginal awareness training for non-Aboriginal union representatives and leadership training programmes for Aboriginal members (Mills and Clarke 2009). In general, public sector unions have been more proactive regarding the needs of Aboriginal members than their private sector counterparts.

Furthermore, unions representing workers in comprehensive land claim settlement areas have changed or adapted their practices because of the increased role of Aboriginal governments in employment. However, there is little information regarding the interactions between unions and Aboriginal peoples in the context of the employment provisions set forth in IBAs. Some attention has been paid to the factors that facilitate the ability of Aboriginal governments to negotiate IBAs, but few have examined these agreements from an employment-relations perspective.

2. The Global Mining Industry and Voisey's Bay

The contemporary structure of the mining industry and other large-scale resource extraction and processing sectors is critical to the experiences of Aboriginal and non-Aboriginal workers. Mining directly accounts for 3.3 per cent of Canada's GDP. Related industries, such as processing, supply and logistics, and transportation account for another 5 per cent (Peters, 2011, p. 80). Canada's mining sector accounts for a particularly large proportion of global market share in three key resources: potash (33 per cent), uranium (23 per cent), and nickel (16 per cent).

Nickel mining has been important to the development of the Canadian economy since the early 20th century. Sudbury is the traditional epicenter of Canadian nickel production, and smaller deposits are also located near Thompson, Manitoba. A large refinery is also located in Port Colborne, Ontario. Until recently, the primary firm involved in the extraction and refining of nickel in Canada was the Toronto-based Inco Ltd.

Since 2000, two trends have been evident in the global mining industry. First, firms have mobilized quickly to take advantage of rising commodity prices. The price of nickel, for example, more than tripled in value between 2002 and 2007 (Figure 1). Second, the industry has consolidated, and large firms such as BHP Billiton, Xstrata, and Rio Tinto have

'quickly swallowed up smaller rivals in the attempt to take more market share, boost capital assets, and diversify their operations' (Peters, 2011, p. 82). Consolidation allows firms to strengthen their control over the supply and pricing of key commodities.

Inco and its subsidiary at Voisey's Bay were not exempt from these trends. In October 2006, the Brazil-based Companhia Vale do Rio Doce (or 'Vale' for short) acquired Inco for \$18.9 billion. Vale's portfolio is diversified, and includes nickel, iron ore, copper, aluminum, coal, and manganese mines and refineries. Originally established as an independent but integrated corporate subsidiary 'Vale-Inco,' the parent firm has since shortened the name to Vale and reduced the autonomy of 'independent' Canadian managers and executives.

Figure 1 - Nickel Price Index, 2000-2010 (2002 = 100)

Source: Statistics Canada, 2011 (CANSIM Table 329-0063)

The Vale takeover in 2006 affected industrial relations in two ways: First, the nickel mined at Voisey's Bay, Sudbury, and Thompson once represented the vast majority of Inco's business. Work stoppages – especially a coordinated strike – were therefore extremely disruptive. As divisions of Vale, however, these three mines together account for a much lower proportion of the parent company's total production. Work stoppages are therefore much less disruptive to the parent company's aggregate earnings. Moreover, slowing or halting production during periods of depressed commodity prices – as witnessed in 2009 – can benefit Vale, allowing them to stockpile product or delay production until prices recover. Second, employment relations in all Canadian facilities became increasingly tense after acquisition as the Brazilian firm sought to implement an increasingly adversarial managerial approach. This was certainly evident in the lengthy strike at Vale between August 2009 and January 2011, as well as in a six month strike at a USW-organized steel mill owned by Gerdau in Cambridge, Ontario. The nature of employment relations at Voisey's Bay are the focus of the next section.

3. The Industrial Relations Climate at Voisey's Bay

This section examines the industrial relations environment at Voisey's Bay nickel mine during the construction and operations phases. It describe the roles and structures of the unions involved in relation to the industrial relations climate of mining and VBNC and provides context for a discussion of union-IBA interactions.

The Construction Phase and the BCTUs

Between 2002 and 2005, VBNC acquired and administered a network of contractors to design, organize logistics, and build the mine, concentrator, and related infrastructure. Through the Voisey's Bay Employers' Association, the parent company and contractors entered into a collective agreement with the RDC that would govern the construction phase of the project. This ensured that members of Newfoundland and Labrador's BCTUs would perform all of the work during the construction phase.

The history of BCTUs can be traced back to the original craft unions. North American craft unions rose to prominence in the latter part of the 19th century, and are strongly influenced by the principles of business unionism espoused by the American Federation of Labor. Business unionism purports that the primary role of unions is to service members and achieves this through top-down structures. Trade unions to organize workers based on specific trades, occupations, and skill sets and are divided into the civil trades (such as carpenters, labourers, ironworkers, and painters) and mechanical trades (such as electricians, plumbers, and pipefitters).

Trade unions help mitigate the effects of the oft-unstable, cyclical, and seasonal patterns in the construction industry (Erlach and Grabelsky, 2005). They increase worker security by facilitating movement between jobs and regions and by providing collective health benefits and pension plans. For employers, trade unions mitigate skilled labour shortages by providing ready access to large pools of highly skilled workers through their role in recruitment and training. Since ensuring a consistent supply of skilled workers is particularly difficult in large-scale industrial and infrastructural projects, building and construction trade unions are more prominent in these sectors than in lighter commercial and residential construction sectors. This 'hiring hall' function helps to mobilize workers in relatively short order. Trade unions also establish uniform terms and conditions for their members and contractors. This is important to tradespersons and construction contractors alike. For tradespersons, consistency ensures that they are remunerated adequately and are not subject to sub-standard working conditions. For union contractors – many of whom are very familiar with trade unions, and some of whom are former members – uniform terms assist with cost estimation and reduce the volatility that occurs during bidding wars between competitors (Erlach and Grabelsky, 2005).

The bargaining power of trade unions comes from the ability to control the supply of skilled labour within a geographic region. Therefore, trade unions have a long-term incentive to organize non-union workers into their membership to maintain their labour market power. However, because work is allocated through a hiring list, unions are often

reluctant to bring in new members particularly in times of high unemployment so as not to dilute the jobs available to members. Moreover, since the basis of union power lies in controlling *skilled* work, trade unions are inclined to restrict access to their trade to maintain their privileged status vis-à-vis 'unskilled' workers. Therefore many unions will accept journey persons as members – since they are already skilled workers – while restricting the entry of new apprentices, thereby limiting the number of skilled workers in the future. In Newfoundland and Labrador this structural imperative is amplified by the high unemployment within union memberships the shortage of apprentice positions that results from high regional unemployment. Many unions therefore do not readily accept new members, or require that they accept positions in western Canada as apprentices prior to working in the province.

Some unions' tendency to limit new members acts as a barrier to Aboriginal workers. Membership restrictions within trade unions often follow racialized or gendered lines. Historically, many trade unions formally excluded women and people of colour from their ranks. These groups of workers continue to be under represented in the skilled trades overall in Canada despite programmes to promote their inclusion. In Canada in 2007, women comprised only 8.5 percent of all trade certificates granted, 78% of which were trades related to food services (Skof, 2010). Some US affiliates of the international BCTUs have made efforts to increase the access of people of African-American and Latino descent to the trades through affirmative action (Erllich and Grabelsky, 2005). Canadian affiliates, however, have not enacted similar programmes to any significant degree. Moreover, there has been little success at increasing the participation of women in trade unions in Canada or the US.

Geography is a significant determinant of trade union membership and access to training, apprenticeships, and certification in Newfoundland and Labrador. Classroom training is provided by a combination of publicly funded colleges and union-affiliated training centres. The provincial government funds a portion of classroom training, although it does not fund travel or accommodation. As a requirement of this funding trade unions are required to provide access to training programmes. Training for apprenticeship levels for some trades is offered on a periodic basis at the College of the North Atlantic in Happy Valley-Goose Bay. All union-operated training centers are located in Newfoundland. There are significant barriers to access to apprenticeships and membership in trade unions. All of the provincial offices of the trade unions belonging to the RDC are located in the Avalon peninsula, and access to apprenticeship hours privilege those who live in or near St. John's, are geographically mobile, and have personal connections that provide prioritized access to union membership or apprenticeship hours. Moreover, there is an historical tendency for trade union members from Newfoundland and Labrador to migrate to western Canada for work. As a result, the RDC-affiliated trade unions – despite having fewer members or apprentices in Labrador – saw Voisey's Bay as an opportunity to have their members working within the province. In fact, many trade union members saw these opportunities as a reward for stoically persisting through years of travel to and from western Canada for the purposes of employment in their trade.

The nature of construction work is also unique in that scheduling, planning, logistics, and coordination between multiple contractors are significant determinants of the pace and success of individual projects. The omnipresent risk of unforeseen disruptions due to a lack of supplies and equipment, inclement weather, and worker shortages are generally accepted as a part of the business. In the case of the mining industry, where developments often occur due to the expectation of strong commodity prices, there is an added impetus to ensure that construction is not delayed. Any delays may prove costly and limit the ability of mining companies to capitalize on rising commodity prices. This was certainly the case at Voisey's Bay, where construction of the mine was completed immediately prior to record increases in the price of nickel between 2006 and 2008.

The Operations Phase and the USW

The operations phase of the mine was not governed by the SPA therefore workers were not organized prior to beginning their employment. The USW became the certified bargaining agent of workers employed directly by VBNC soon after the mine and concentrator opened in 2005. The union then organized workers employed by subcontractors Ushitau Maintenance, Torngait Services, Labrador Catering, and ASC Innu Security Limited between 2005 and 2009. Each subcontractor was organized into separate bargaining units within the same local as the VBNC employees. The USW was well positioned to represent the workers given their longstanding presence in Labrador City and their experience in the nickel industry and with Inco, where they represented employees at the nickel mines in Sudbury and Thompson and at a refinery in Port Colborne. Traditionally, employment relations between the USW and Canadian nickel mining firms Inco and Falconbridge were mildly adversarial, and strikes were not uncommon. USW locals were often successful in their bargaining efforts because of their ability to stop production across operations. Sharing identities based on their occupations, owners, managers, and unionized workers accepted the occasional strike as a part of the business. Voisey's Bay presented challenges to the USW's traditional practices. Being a newer operation, labour practices at Voisey's Bay diverged from those of older nickel mines in Canada. Following broader trends in mining labour practices, VNBC relied on a highly mobile workforce, a sophisticated and capital intensive operation, and a heightened use of on-site sub-contractors (Dansereau, 2006).

Unlike Sudbury and Thompson, where urban communities were developed near mineral deposits, no permanent settlement was established at Voisey's Bay, and VBNC employs workers on a fly-in/fly-out basis. This is consistent with broader trends in mining and resource development, where firms are increasingly hesitant to invest in the infrastructure required to sustain a permanent community since technological developments increasing productivity have shortened the lifespan of individual mines (Dansereau, 2006). Fly-in/fly-out arrangements are advantageous for many Aboriginal employees since it allows workers to reside in their home community while working at a distant mine. However, some suggest that fly-in/fly-out arrangements create challenges for familial life and increase fragmentation among workers and between workers and management. Whereby permanent mining communities created a shared sense of identity and community, the move to fly-in/fly-out increases the cost and difficulty of communication with workers

since employers control access to the site and workers are geographically dispersed in their off time. Communication challenges make collective organizing more expensive and challenging and limit the effectiveness of strike actions. Communication between off-shift employees and both their union and employer can also be difficult, especially when the former reside in remote communities.

The capital-intensive nature of contemporary mining has also increased job-skill requirements and concomitantly reduced the number of manual and unskilled entry-level jobs. By increasing labour productivity, new technology has reduced the total number of workers needed. Although higher labour productivity allows the firm to offer higher wages and improve occupational health and safety, it also increases the skill requirements for employment and provides a rationale for the employer to disregard seniority.

Furthermore, global mining corporations increasingly contract out various functions of production and maintenance. This is done to control costs and reduce risk. VBNC is no exception, and important but lower value-added functions like security, catering, and transportation services are operated by independent contractors. In most cases, the wages, benefits, and working conditions of the employees of contractors are far below those of employees of the parent firm. The employees of contractors are also less likely to be covered by the terms and conditions of a collective agreement.

These challenges notwithstanding, the USW was in a position to improve wages, benefits, and working conditions at Voisey's Bay. Representing workers in other parts of Canada also gave the USW first-hand knowledge to ensure that the wages, benefits, and other terms and conditions were in line with national trends. The USW was also able to mitigate the common tendency for non-core workers to receive sub-standard wages or working conditions by negotiating collective agreements for sub-contractors that were consistent with the VBNC agreement.

4. Institutional Analysis of Employment Governance

The parties responsible for governing employment and employment relations at Voisey's Bay included the NG, the VBNC, the BCTUs, and the USW. This section focuses on how labour unions interacted with NG in relation to the provisions in the IBA.

Construction Phase

The relationships among the NG, the VBNC, BCTUs, and contractors during the construction phase were institutionalized through both the IBA and a Special Project Agreement (SPA) negotiated between the RDC and the VBNC. The IBA negotiated between the NG and the VBNC outlined an order of preference founded in Aboriginal rights and the concept of adjacency - that those living closest to the development should have priority for jobs. As a result, Inuit beneficiaries from Nain or Innu from Natuashish were to be considered for employment first, followed by other Inuit on the coast, Innu and Inuit elsewhere in Labrador, and finally beneficiaries living outside of the province. Female beneficiaries were also prioritized in the IBA, and were to have precedence over male Inuit or Innu irrespective of location of residence. These provisions were included in only a general fashion in the SPA. Language referring to the IBA and the order of preference in the collective agreement was weak, stating that the agreement "*ensures participation of Labrador Inuit and Labrador Innu employees*" (SPA 2002, 1) and that "the Council, their member Unions, the Association and all Contractors agree to *co-operate* with the (IBA) requirements ... to allow these commitments to be fulfilled to the maximum *extent possible*." (SPA 2002, 4; our emphasis). Furthermore, the collective agreement stated that "All hiring will be done through the Council office," (SPA 2002, 7), institutionalizing the RDC's role in recruitment and job assignment. Yet the onus for fulfilling the IBA requirements was left with contractors. Consequently, not only was there no clear process for hiring qualified Inuit and Innu who were not BCTU members, but there was also no institutional clarity. The SPA did state, however, that beneficiaries hired through the IBA needed to become union members prior to starting work. This requirement meant that many Inuit and Innu were required to pay substantial sums of money to work on the site since BCTUs typically have initiation fees of over a thousand dollars. In general, there was a disconnect between the IBA, that contained precise language stipulating order of hiring preference based on identity status, and the SPA, that contained precise language on hiring procedures following union hiring lists.

Construction began soon after the IBA was signed, and the NG felt that they did not have sufficient time to establish mechanisms to enforce the terms and conditions of the IBA. In the absence of a clearly defined hiring process to follow the order of preference, contractors followed established norms at the beginning of construction. According to one NG representative:

"It was the words of yes, we'll make sure we hire people but then the how part never really got translated until we worked out the processes afterwards. So there was no step-by-step up front (process)... during the construction (phase) of the project." (P57)

Only after the start of construction, did the NG and VBNC together create a process for identifying beneficiaries for new positions. Contractors were required to send all requests for hires to the IBA Training and Employment coordinator prior to looking outside. Even after a process was established, however, a lack of trust remained; from the perspective of the NG, trade unions and contractors were outsiders bent on providing employment to their own members at the expense of Inuit and Innu workers.

Some contractors and BCTUs were initially reluctant to include IBA provisions in the SPA. Contractors were concerned that hiring Inuit and Innu, who they perceived to be less skilled, would jeopardize their ability to meet production schedules within defined costs. The BCTUs, for their part, wanted to ensure both that their members obtained work on the project, and that they maintained control over the speed and quality of work, which they felt was best achieved by hiring their own members. This point made many unions during negotiations. As expressed by one trade union business manager: “We cannot control work productivity for a group of people who aren’t trained and/or could potentially have not been trained” (P38). Quality and efficiency were not only embedded in the culture of construction, they were employer requirements stipulated in the SPA. For employers, the stated purpose of an SPA, is:

“... to achieve uninterrupted completion of the Project, on time, at the least budget cost and with “0” defects while achieving the highest level of performance consistent with safety, good health and sustained effort.” (SPA 2002, 1)

Moreover, and unlike the VBNC, trade unions and contractors lacked long-term commitments to the Inuit, Innu, and other residents of Labrador. Only the Carpenters union had undertaken significant organizing in Labrador. Instead, most trade unions concentrated on servicing their Newfoundland memberships, investing little in organizing activities. There were exceptions however, and several locals had removed restrictions on new members with the aim of revitalizing their locals.

Skill requirements became a key way that unions were able to ensure that their members obtained work on the project. The civil trades therefore took in greater numbers of new members than the mechanical trades who generally had skill requirements limiting job competition between pre-existing Newfoundland members and Innu and Inuit applicants. In some cases, however, the designation of qualifications required for a job was more subjective. Trade unions and contractors were able to capitalize on their knowledge of documented skill sets of individual (non-Aboriginal) union members in order to circumvent their responsibilities outlined in the IBA. One VBNC manager describes these practices in some detail:

“[Contractors] would put a request together that was so specific that they would make sure their buddy got hired. That’s what you really had to be conscious of. [...] They would do that quite often.” (P66)

Such practices demonstrate how the hiring list system of trade unions, while providing worker protection, can also perpetuate systemic discrimination. With little prior organizing in Aboriginal communities there was no incentive for unions to hire Aboriginal workers, moreover pre-conceptions that Aboriginal workers would not have sufficient skills for the work threatened BCTUs' sense of control over the quality of their work.

The VBNC's relationship with the NG was much different. This was due to the long-term nature of their interests – something that the trade unions and affiliated contractors did not share – and the fact that the VBNC was directly involved in negotiating and administering many aspects of the IBA. One VBNC manager described the efforts taken by the NG employment coordinators to convince representatives of the RDC that the IBA was a legitimate document to which they must adhere:

“...they ... met with the sixteen representatives of the RDC and explain(ed) to them [...] that this is an IBA. This is what it means to this company... This is not some sort of wishy-washy thing that is nice to do ... this is ... a contractual agreement.” (P66)

It took the coordinated efforts of the NG and VBNC managers – whose actions were based on mutual interests – to communicate to construction contractors and trade unions that the provisions of the IBA were legitimate. These mutual interests helped the two parties to establish a relationship as they moved into the operations phase.

Operations Phase

The agreements governing employment relations during the operations phase at Voisey's Bay are the IBA and the collective agreements between the USW, the VBNC, and affiliated contractors. Fundamentally, these agreements are designed to ensure that a greater share of the economic benefits from the extraction and refining of minerals flow to LILCA beneficiaries and VBNC employees. The NG is primarily concerned with ensuring that economic benefits of development are shared with Labrador Inuit, while the USW is concerned with ensuring that benefits are shared by Aboriginal and non-Aboriginal workers alike.

IBA language specifying the order of preference in hiring and promotion was included in USW collective agreements despite the fact that USW did not have jurisdiction over hiring. Only in the case of promotion did order of preference provisions require a shift in traditional union practices. Stipulations regarding promotion based on order of preference represented a break from the USW's traditional focus on seniority (although seniority still applies within specific preference groups and in relation to vacation schedules). The inclusion of this language signified the USW's willingness to recognize the NG as a legitimate agent with jurisdiction over specific matters related to production and employment at Voisey's Bay. The collective agreements contained additional language designed to assist the progression of Inuit and Innu workers into higher skilled and better-paying jobs by allowing trial promotions that facilitate on-the-job training. In general, stipulations regarding the order of preference were featured more prominently and included clauses related to hiring and promotion that the SPA lacked (Appendix B).

Despite the inclusion of a more detailed order of preference in the collective agreement, some points of contention hindered the development of a constructive relationship between the NG and the USW. The different priorities and purpose of each party created conflicting understandings of their respective jurisdiction over employment matters as well distrust of the other organizations' commitment to Inuit workers.

As a government, the NG made decisions on behalf of all of its members, not only those working at Voisey's Bay. Although employment opportunities were an important way NG members could benefit from the Voisey's Bay development, they were not the only economic benefit to Inuit. In the realm of employment, NG representatives were more concerned with equality among Inuit than with maintaining wage and benefit parity with other mines across Canada. In particular, NG wanted to ensure that Inuit on the coast who were historically disadvantaged in the labour market would benefit from the work at Voisey's Bay. In contrast, the USW was concerned with improving working conditions, pay, and benefits for all workers at Voisey's Bay. USW representatives felt that the NG's preoccupation with *economic* benefits such as royalties rather than *employment* benefits was detrimental to Inuit workers. They viewed this as contradictory since in their minds improving the terms and conditions of work benefited Inuit. The organizations' divergent views on their respective purposes surfaced during the 2009-2011 strike. Several Inuit union members asked that the NG support the striking workers. The NG drew on their understanding of employment governance to maintain that they could not evoke the IBA to support the strikers:

"They say 'well we voted for the IBA' and we have to constantly remind them yes, you voted for the IBA, every member of Nunatsiavut had the opportunity to vote for the IBA. You voted for the union agreement to become a unionized site. It's only a certain select few who had the opportunity to do that. It's an employer-employee thing, it's not a Nunatsiavut Government fight..." (P57)

The NG clearly distinguished that their role of enforcing the IBA was separate from what they understood to be the role of the union: enforcing collective agreements. Since the beginning of the project the VBNC kept their relationships with the RDC, the USW, and the NG separate. A management representative described his perception that the Aboriginal groups did not need, and were not interested in whether workers had collective representation. In his words:

"...it's irrelevant to them if it were a union site or a non-union site. They're going to keep [our] feet to the fire and say, 'are you living up to the agreements that we have in the IBA? ... are you providing opportunities to our businesses and are you providing opportunities to our members for employment?' As long as we continue to do that then we will keep the governments of the Innu and Inuit happy." (P66)

In contrast with NG's desire to draw a firm line between their role and that of the union, the USW had a less rigid view of jurisdiction. The USW sought to bargain clauses that

paralleled the IBA (over and above the hiring and promotion clauses mentioned above) in collective agreements. Their attempt followed from strategies used by other unions in workplaces covered by IBAs, who have used collective agreements to strengthen, supplement and enforce terms and conditions in IBAs. Throughout bargaining, the VBNC and the NG resisted the USW's strategy of improving worker conditions by including IBA stipulations in their collective agreement. As described by one USW representative:

I: ...it's much better for it to be in the collective agreement?

P56: Yes, that's right, and then we have some form of [...] recourse when you see the company infringing on those rights.

I: The Nunatsiavut Government resisted you on this?

P56: Yes, they did.

I: Why do you think that is?

P56: I think that they had issues with the union policing their Impacts and Benefits Agreement. (P56)

The company (supported by the NG) resisted the negotiation of IBA provisions, or any clauses that resembled IBA provisions in collective agreement. Despite this, the USW was able to negotiate some clauses specific to Aboriginal workers. As one representative noted:

"We wanted to negotiate paid cultural leave as opposed to the current practice of unpaid leave. [...] we wanted to build on Aboriginal rights. We actually negotiated National Aboriginal Day as a [paid] stat holiday in our first collective agreement." (P58)

Just as the NG did not see themselves as having a role in industrial relations disputes, they did not see the USW as having a role in negotiating or enforcing IBA provisions. One of the foremost reasons for this is that the NG did not negotiate the IBA with the USW in mind. Rather, they negotiated it in partnership with the VBNC. The terms and conditions outlined in the IBA, such as cultural leave, were perceived by NG representatives to be static and no longer the subject of negotiations. One representative discussed this in detail:

"...we were saying 'well I don't care what you do' – and this is to the company internally - saying 'don't care what you do with the USW, but you need to make sure that we have provisions in there, that our IBA provisions are respected.' [...] there were a lot of questions when they were doing the first collective agreement about that particular implementation. You know I mean, they [USW representatives] would call and say 'well cultural leave, what is that, what do we do about that?' And I said well whatever you do Aboriginal people have a right to take cultural leave, it's unpaid, these are the conditions, you can't mess with it." (P57)

Furthermore, the IBA was negotiated as a private agreement between the NG and the VBNC, while collective agreements between the USW and the publicly traded firms Inco and Vale are widely available. There may also be some concern that by publicizing the IBA and including it in collective agreements, the NG may be required to cede control over its

adjudication to the provincial labour board, with which the USW is more experienced. For NG representatives, such a shift was also contrary to the spirit and intent of the IBA and posed a potential threat to self-governance. Lastly, the NG were concerned that negotiating IBA clauses into collective agreements would jeopardize the rights of their members by providing non-Aboriginal workers with the same entitlements as Inuit workers.

Though both unions and the NG aimed to increase the flow of benefits from resource development to people living in Newfoundland and Labrador, the different purposes of each organization created challenges to communication among groups and tension in relation to the hiring and representation of Aboriginal peoples. These differences were reflected in workers' perceptions of the IBA, the union, and their experiences of work.

5. Impacts of Unions and the IBA on Employment Relations: Workers' Perspectives

Three themes emerged from the worker interviews: access to employment, training and lack of clarity in workplace governance. Worker's perceptions within each of these themes corresponded to their location of residence. In our sample, location of residence was closely related to, and therefore can serve as a proxy for, a participants' self-declared membership in an Aboriginal group. Participants from the coastal community of Nain all identified as Inuit and members of the NG. Only one participant from Goose Bay identified as non-Aboriginal and all Innu participants lived in Sheshatshiu. No individuals from Newfoundland identified as Aboriginal.

Access to Employment

Limited employment opportunities in Newfoundland and Labrador, and particularly in Inuit and Innu communities made access to employment at Voisey's Bay particularly contentious. To determine whether workers agreed with the order of preference in hiring, we asked them to order identity groups in terms of hiring priority at the mine and mill. Their thoughts revealed beliefs and assumptions about who is entitled to employment and whether they agreed with the IBA. Some non-Aboriginal workers described the order of preference as unjust. One male Newfoundlander working in operations felt that the order of preference was justified at the hiring stage, but that layoffs should follow reverse order of seniority:

"I don't agree with being laid off first because I'm from Newfoundland ...we've had people consult with lawyers about that...I guess it's kind of a violation of my constitutional right, to lay me off because I'm from Newfoundland." (P19)

This man's discontent with differential lay-off practices reflected his experience with and belief in union seniority practices. Since the USW did not play a role in hiring, preferential hiring did not violate seniority; however, prioritizing Inuit and Innu in layoffs did. The worker drew on the notion of universal rights to justify his position. Another Newfoundlander also referred to the idea of equality and universal human rights when describing why he felt Aboriginal people should not be hired first for jobs:

P5: Priority? No, it should be equal.

I: So why do you think that it should be in that order?

P5: Well...because we are the same province right? So me as a Newfoundlander I feel that I'm just as important ... Right here #2 the most qualified person. (P5)

This worker felt that all people in the province should have equal access to work in the province. He therefore felt that place of residence was an important criterion for employment – but only at the scale of the province. Within the province he felt that the most qualified people should get the job, indicating that he believed in meritocracy.

Meritocracy is the western liberal idea that people who work hard should be, and are, rewarded by greater power and opportunity – in this case access to employment and promotion. Individual merit is measured by one’s skills and education, which are seen to be a direct result of personal effort. From this perspective, qualifications should be the only criteria that entitle people for jobs. Although subscribing to meritocracy is commonplace in western society, it has been criticized for its disregard of pre-existing inequality. Intergenerational inequality in power, wealth, and resources shape the distribution of skills and education in society, and therefore, who is deemed to have ‘merit.’ From this perspective meritocracy does not create equality, but maintains the status quo, reproducing patterns of disadvantage and privilege. For example, colonial practices and policies that dispossessed Aboriginal peoples from their lands and resources led to their systemic disadvantage in formal education, business ownership, and the labour market.

By restoring access to wealth from lands and resources, land claims and IBAs seek to reverse patterns of historical dispossession. Originating in the Labrador Inuit claim to lands including Voisey’s Bay, the order of preference was therefore grounded in Aboriginal rights to lands (now referred to as Aboriginal title) rather than a notion of liberal equality. The legitimacy of rights to lands and resources as a basis for employment was not lost on all Newfoundlanders, however. When asked to explain why she thought Inuit and Innu should have priority for jobs, one non-Aboriginal woman stated: “I just think that’s the way it should be. It’s theirs. I look at it that way...They should get some benefit from it” (P25). This woman felt that Labrador Innu and Inuit should be privileged for work since in her mind they owned the minerals being extracted.

Several Inuit workers also described relationship to territory as the primary basis for employment. One worker from Nain supported the order of preference describing how the Inuit and Innu who used Voisey’s Bay historically should have greater rights to jobs:

“The way I look at it is Nain is the closest place... there are enough people from Nain, hire them, if they can’t then you go to Natuashish because Natuashish is the second closest community to Voisey’s Bay and both Inuit and Innu both use the bottom of Voisey’s Bay in the past. And then from there, then you work your way down [the coast].” (P11)

According to this perspective, rights to employment flow from land rights. Inuit from Nain and Goose Bay and Innu from Shetshatshiu supported the order of preference for hiring, layoff, and recall. Moreover, nine people felt that they would not have been hired without it. One Inuk stated that “if we didn’t have that [the IBA]...I don’t think very many Labradorians, be it Innu or Inuit, would be working up there right now” (P13). The prevalence of these comments among Inuit and Innu suggests that many Aboriginal workers had either experienced or observed employment discrimination on the basis of Aboriginality in the past. One Inuk described how the IBA was important to counter the employer’s preference for hiring Newfoundland workers:

“I probably would have had to fight harder to get a job because a lot of times what these people do, they bring in a lot of outsiders. Usually people from Newfoundland [are hired] before [people from] Labrador. Even though a lot of Labradorians are trained and for some reason, they like to hire Newfoundlanders first. I don’t know why.” (P9)

Of interview participants, very few described incidents of discrimination on the basis of Aboriginal identity. However, several Inuit women working in male-dominated job classifications described feeling that they had to work harder than men to prove that they were competent workers.

“At first it was a bit hard with the Ironworkers, with the construction phase, but once they got to know you could do the work it was easy enough ... ‘cause you’re a woman. You have to prove yourself when you’re a woman.” (P23)

Another woman described having to fight to be promoted:

“It’s hard for us to get promoted. We have to fight really hard. And it’s very frustrating because guys are just given opportunities no sweat. ... since I started I never had a promotion until last year ... I had to fight in order to get promoted.... It’s pretty sad. I didn’t want to do it that way... Guys are getting promoted left, right, and centre, people hired after me was getting promoted and I’m like ‘what? what’s going on?’” (P22)

These results follow patterns observed in other studies of women’s experiences in male-dominated work environments (Reed, 2003; Sweeney, 2010). Previous research on women working in resource industries and as firefighters and police officers also demonstrates that women working in male-dominated environments face heightened harassment and pressure to prove themselves (Yoder, 1991). Although the IBA stated that Inuit women should be given preference over Inuit men, this requirement was not able to address the exclusion women faced as a result of a male dominated mining culture and the small proportion of women on site.

Training

Several Inuit workers felt that gaps in qualifications between Aboriginal and non-Aboriginal peoples needed to be addressed for Inuit to fully benefit from employment opportunities at the mine. The observation that training was linked to local employment benefits reflected an understanding that Inuit and Innu, particularly those living on the coast, face considerable barriers to accessing training and employment opportunities.

Prior training and work experience of interviewees was related to their location of residence and their sex. Male Inuit from Goose Bay often had some industrial work experience and training prior to working at VBNC; half of the men had also worked at

SERCO – the company that provides maintenance for the nearby military base. A minority of participants in Goose Bay held a journeyman certificate in a trade. Most had attended a pre-employment programme for Voisey's Bay at the College of the North Atlantic. Women interviewed from Goose Bay had work experience in caring (e.g. health care) occupations or in retail work. There were fewer employment opportunities in Nain with the result that many workers from this community had little or no training prior to working at Voisey's Bay. They also had less varied employment histories. Participants from Sheshatshiu had the lowest levels of training, and no Innu participants had previous experience in a recognized trade. Two participants had no previous employment history. Men and women from Newfoundland had more extensive work experience, often in the mining industry. Most Newfoundland participants were senior apprentices, journeymen, or had considerable experience in their field of expertise. A similar proportion of Inuit men and women had formal training prior to working at VBNC. No Innu women and only one male Innu reported receiving formal training and none worked in the skilled trades.

Because of the IBA provisions, workers from Newfoundland were only hired if no Innu or Inuit had the required skills. The over-representation of Newfoundlanders in more highly skilled positions speaks to the structural barriers Labrador Inuit and Innu face to gaining employment experience and training opportunities. The majority of skilled trade apprenticeships are not offered in Labrador. As a result, to become a journeyman it is necessary to travel to Newfoundland or other parts of Canada. Barriers to training and employment are thus amplified for Inuit living on the coast of Labrador because of the high cost of travel and the absence of significant employment development or training programmes in their communities. Accordingly, in our sample only two Inuit from Nain and one Innu from Sheshatshiu had college or apprenticeship training, while all workers from Goose Bay had some form of training. That said, there were several cases of workers from Nain who had considerable skills without formal qualification. This was most common when someone had experience in a trade but had not worked under the supervision of a journeyman or if they had not completed the schooling required to be considered for an apprenticeship.

Although many Inuit felt that the order of preference should also consider qualifications, several respondents felt that Innu or Inuit should be hired first irrespective of whether they had the required qualifications. In some cases, such as the following exchange, the disregard for qualifications reflected egalitarian values.

I: Why do you think people with qualifications should be (hired) last?

P15: Because they're qualified and they can do whatever they want...they can...apply for a job and get it. They can help themselves. (P15)

The above statement communicated this Inuk's belief in first helping those who were most in need, rather than rewarding those who have merit. He understood equality in terms of outcomes.

Measuring the success of the IBA on the basis of outcomes underscores the need to rectify the barriers that Inuit face that make it difficult to access training and education. Another

Inuk suggested that the company should address their human resource needs through training rather than through external hiring, stating:

P6: ...if they [the company] are not getting any qualified people looking for work then they should actually go out and start recruiting within the school systems and put them through qualified schooling.

I: The school systems in Labrador?

P6: Yes ...within the Nunatsiavut beneficiaries land claims areas...And get that interest in the younger people to get them to want to come and work for them...they should be actively pursuing those avenues. (P6)

This worker's recommendation that the company provide training so that Inuit and Innu have the qualifications for all of the jobs needed demonstrated his awareness that Inuit will not receive full employment benefits from resource development so long as they can be excluded on the basis of qualifications. Given the unequal access to schooling and distribution of qualifications, training programmes are essential to ensure that Inuit and Innu are well represented at all job levels in resource development projects.

Lack of Clarity in Workplace Governance

Since non-Aboriginal workers are not covered by the IBA they had little to no contact with the NG. Their opinions regarding the NG were therefore minimal, save for some who expressed their wishes that the NG would do more to bring an end to the strike. Because Inuit workers' employment is governed by both the IBA and collective agreements, respondents often expressed confusion over the respective roles and responsibilities of the USW and NG regarding their employment-related welfare.

Several factors contributed to confusion over workplace governance. First, both the IBA (through the NG) and unions professed to protect Inuit workers and improve their employment experiences. For example, Vale's Inuit and Innu Employment Coordinators on site were akin to shop stewards since their role was to address concerns of Inuit workers (albeit related to the IBA). This placed the onus of determining workplace jurisdiction over a grievance or complaint on individual workers. Moreover, when asked if the IBA affected their work experience, several Inuit stated that the primary role of the IBA was worker protection, a role typically understood to be the purview of unions. One Inuk replied by stating "(the IBA) provides work protection and opportunity that you wouldn't have before" (P18). The IBA provided worker protection for Inuit in the same way union seniority provides protection for unionized workers, by establishing a clear order of layoff and recall.

Requiring that workers assess the jurisdiction of each institution was complicated by the fact that many Innu and Inuit living on the coast had little experience with unions prior to working at Voisey’s Bay. The disparity in union experience was noted by union and NG representatives and was also reflected in our sample. This is illustrated in Table 4. Most workers in our sample had more experience with construction unions than with industrial unions. Women in the sample were also less likely to have union experience prior to working at Voisey’ Bay.

Table 4 – Union Experience by Gender and Ethnicity

Previous Union Experience?	Identity					
	Inuit Male	Inuit Female	Innu Male	Innu Female	Other Male	Other Female
Yes	5	1	0	0	4	1
No	11	5	3	3	1	2

Inuit workers were often unsure whether to approach the USW or the NG with work-related concerns. Although some Inuit clearly stated that the union represented them as workers, others noted that they had approached the NG for employment-related help in the past. When asked if they had ever gone to the NG for help, one Inuit worker described using the NG as a last resort to resolve an incident with a coworker, stating “it felt like nobody was helping me at first and I felt all alone so I actually called my President [of the NG].” Going to NG for work-related help was not universal, and most Inuit workers saw the union as their first line of contact in a dispute. One Nain resident claimed that:

P1: “I think it’s more go to the union, everybody’s understanding, thinking let’s take care of it in house... if there is a problem with your supervisor, ...it’s not like, oh let’s go to Nunatsiavut Government, no it’s more go to the union.”
(P1)

Although most workers claimed to have never approached the NG for help with work-related matters, those that had were often disappointed with the support they received. Several people expressed dissatisfaction with the Innu or Inuit Employment Monitors - who they mistood to be representatives of NG - when they approached them for help. Several people felt that Innu and Inuit Employment Monitors, hired by VBNC, were not able to assist them. One Inuk felt that Inuit and Innu Employment Monitors were unable to assist workers since they were employed by VBNC:

I: Have you approached the Nunatsiavut Government for help with anything work related?
P3: No, other than to have a stroll over and have the occasional chat in the first few years with the Employment Monitor which quickly became apparent to me was a waste of breath.

P3: "I've gone to the representative for Nunatsiavut...the Employment Monitor ...She is employed by Vale so I mean as long as she gets a paycheque, what is it to her right?" (P3)

During the strike, many Inuit felt that it was the NG's responsibility to look after the welfare of beneficiaries employed at VBNC. These feelings are summed up in the following passage.

I: ...have you approached the Nunatsiavut Government for help...?

P20: I did. I tried to ask before [but] they never gave me no help. They said we got nothing to do with [Vale Inco]. I said, 'how can you have nothing to do with that? That mine is in your backyard and I'm a beneficiary'." (P20)

This worker felt that the NG was responsible for enforcing work conditions as an extension of the government's role enforcing the IBA. This view conflicted with the NG's understanding that their jurisdiction over employment ended where that of the union began.

Workers were most divided in their beliefs about the role of that the NG should be playing in the strike. Some expressed the opinion that the government should be doing more to end the strike while others defended the government, stating that it had its hands tied by the IBA. Those who claimed the NG was unable to assist due to the IBA felt as though the union was misinforming its membership and trying to cause conflict among LILCA beneficiaries. They claimed that the misinformation stemmed from a lack of understanding of the IBA. This is evident in the following quotes:

"There was just a lot of concerns and false propaganda about the Nunatsiavut Government saying that the Nunatsiavut Government don't care about its people, they are allowing the boat to come in and just foolishness like that...They haven't even read the IBA. I asked them personally, I asked the president and the vice-president and the former vice-president [of the union] if they read the IBA and the shipping agreement and they said they haven't." (P10)

"This is my second strike with Vale and NG and people are saying why can't NG back us up? But I mean we did our own thing when we became a union, we can't really depend on the NG to back us up after we are part of a union in the first place. Some people just don't understand that." (P12)

Although there was some discord amongst the workers as to the proper role of the NG, a majority of people understood that the limited role of the NG and why they were unable to provide assistance during the strike.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this report suggests that unions have an important role to play in Aboriginal employment but that this role, is one of supporting – and not appropriating – the Aboriginal government’s role in employment.

In particular, the BCTUs are in an ideal position to facilitate the training and employment of Aboriginal workers because of their role in training and employment. First, the organizational structure and culture of the BCTU unions was not conducive to the inclusion of Aboriginal workers. Significant barriers to Aboriginal participation included the absence of organizing prior to the project in remote communities, high membership initiation fees, and structural incentives for memberships to not admit new members. If these barriers were removed, BCTU unions could guide new apprentices through the complex environment of construction work. By placing workers in appropriate apprenticeship positions, facilitating in-school training, ensuring that workers have protection against health and safety violations, and that they receive sufficient pay and benefits and pensions, the BCTUs could support rather than hinder Aboriginal employment and training.

Second, as the NG’s relationship with the USW evolved through the Voisey’s Bay project, each institution developed an understanding of their respective roles in the governance of employment. However, given that these understandings were not always consistent, it is no surprise that Inuit workers expressed mixed understandings and expectations of their unions and their government. Aboriginal governments and unions have a role to play in fostering better communication – both with one another to establish clear understandings of jurisdiction - and with Aboriginal workers to ensure that they are able to fully participate in workplace governance.

Third, and despite the educational programmes provided, several non-Aboriginal workers and some BCTU representatives did not understand (or acknowledge) the territorial basis for the Impact Benefit Agreement order of preference provisions. This suggests that there is a need for improved education for workers and particularly union representatives about Aboriginal title and the history of colonization.

Lastly, given the frequent mergers and acquisitions in the mining sector, Aboriginal communities are going to be negotiating with increasingly large firms that are most often multinational. The increasing size and extra-territoriality of firms limits both the ability of Aboriginal groups to enforce contracts negotiated at a given point in time as well as the ability of unions to collectively organize. The threat of court action to enforce an IBA is rendered less effective when faced with a global company that is able to withstand production delays. Authors have cited concerns about the ability of communities to enforce employment provisions in IBAs in the face of recalcitrant employers (Caine and Krogman, 2010). Given the increasingly globalized nature of mining, ensuring that unions and Aboriginal communities work together is critical to maximizing the employment benefits that Aboriginal communities derive from development.

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APPENDIX A

Order of Preference Clauses

Source: Collective Agreement between VBNC and USW Local 9508 (2006-2009)

12.07 The Order of Preference to be followed in awarding positions to candidates meeting the Standards for the position is as follows:

- a. Innu and Inuit candidates who are members of the VBNC bargaining unit,
- b. Innu and Inuit external candidates who are employed at the Voisey's Bay site (new hire),
- c. Innu and Inuit candidates who are external applicants (new hire),
- d. Labradorian candidates who are members of the VBNC bargaining unit,
- e. Labradorian external candidates who are employed at the Voisey's Bay site (new hire),
- f. Labradorian candidates who are external applicants (new hire),
- g. Other candidates who are members of the VBNC bargaining unit,
- h. Other external candidates who are employed at the Voisey's Bay site (new hire),
- i. Other candidates who are external applicants (new hire).

For greater certainty, persons who occupy preference status (b), (c), (e), (f), (h) and (i) and who are identified above as "new hires" shall enter this bargaining unit as new employees and shall not be entitled to seniority credit for time they may have spent in other Steelworker bargaining units.

APPENDIX B

Additional Clauses Related to Order of Preference

Source: Collective Agreement between VBNC and USW Local 9508 (2006-2009)

- 12.08 Competency training to expand an employee's work scope within a job progression will be offered at each progression level in Order of Preference within the bargaining unit, subject to the employee being able to perform the work required.
- 12.09 Apprenticeship positions will be filled in accordance with the provisions for filling of vacancies.
- 12.10 Employees appointed to a new position shall be subject to a trial period in the new position of two full working rotations at Site. In the event that the Employee proves unsatisfactory in the position during the trial period, or if the employee is unable to perform the duties of the new position, he/she shall return to his/her former position, wage or salary rate and without loss of seniority. Any other employee promoted or transferred because of the rearrangement of positions shall also be returned to his/her former position, wage or salary rate and without loss of seniority. The parties may mutually agree, in writing, to extend the trial period. Where an employee fails to successfully complete a trial period, or voluntarily reverts to his/her former position prior to completion of the trial period, the employee will not be permitted to be considered for the same position for a period of at least twelve (12) months.